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Assembly Twin**

D1.1 Experimental campaign plan and taxonomy

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Abbreviations and acronyms

EIS	Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy
LIB	Lithium ion battery
NIB	Sodium ion battery
RFB	Redox flow battery

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1. Executive summary

Description of the deliverable content and objectives

In this deliverable, the experimental campaign plan necessary for BatCAT is described as well as the methods and nomenclature used to store its data. It is the initial step of the experimental work done since the beginning of the BatCAT project.

The BatCAT project is focusing on the manufacturing of batteries regarding 2 use-cases : Li-ion/Sodium-ion batteries (LIB/NIB) and redox-flow batteries (RFB) and the impact of manufacturing parameters on the operation of the batteries. As a consequence, the experimental campaign accounts for both cell manufacturing but also battery performance during operation. In this deliverable the manufacturing steps considered experimentally in both LIB/NIB and RFB use cases along with the tunable parameters considered in each step are presented. Then the experimental characterization planned for the manufacturing steps as well as the battery operation are described.

Then the data storage system is described by explaining the different files and storage locations used up until now to store the data and metadata of the experiments performed so far. The experimental files are completed by experimental partners of WP1 so that other beneficiaries are able to recover the data as well as the history of samples tested through “recipe” files. This work was performed in collaboration with WP4 to ensure that all necessary data and metadata required in WP4 are available in the information collected in WP1 and at the same time that all data types encountered in WP1 experiments fits within the taxonomy described in WP4.

The information in this deliverable will be used to plan the next steps of the experimental campaign in agreement with requirements of other beneficiaries in the BatCAT project.

Deviation from objectives, corrective action (if applicable)

Final ELN and data storage tools are not running completely up until now as a consequence a provisional solution was adopted using BatCAT SharePoint to ensure a reliable and easy sharing of data among partners.

2. Progress report (main activities)

The work described in this deliverable is focused on 3 main activities:

- Performing specific steps of the manufacturing process to get representative samples which can be further analysed to get their properties and calibrate and validate models
- Analyse these samples
- Store the data in a sensible way so that other BatCAT partners are able to recover and use them in their activities.

In the following section, the experimental campaign, available characterization methods and data storage processes will be described. They cover both use case from the BatCAT project Li-ion and Sodium-ion batteries (LIB/NIB) as well as the redox-flow batteries (RFB).

Experimental campaign description

LIB/NIB use case

The LIB/NIB process is a sequence of several steps from the raw active materials to the final battery cells (Figure 1).

Figure 1: LIB/NIB cell production process

The following parameters must be optimised in the LIB/NIB use cases to ensure optimal device performance. These hold for a single formulation or combination of materials and any changes to the chemistry requires additional optimisation.

Formulation of the coating slurry

Formulations consist of an active material (e.g. NMC, LFP, graphite), a binder (e.g. PVDF) and a conductive additive (e.g. carbon black) to enhance electron conduction. Sometimes, additional additives are included to further enhance device performance (e.g. carbon nanotubes). These “dry” ingredients are mixed stepwise with a solvent to form a slurry which can be coated onto current collectors to form battery electrode anodes and cathodes.

The tuneable control parameters for the slurry formulation are as follows at CPI:

1. Material choices (limited by market availability)
 - a. Active material particle size and distribution
 - b. Conductive additive (carbon black) particle size
 - c. Binder type (informs solvent)
 - d. Additive type (if any)
2. Active material: binder : conductive additive ratio
3. Solids/liquid ratio (solids content)
4. Additive content (e.g. carbon nanotubes)
5. Mixing order
6. Mixing speed

Coating of the slurry onto current collector

Formulation slurries are coated onto current collector foils by a doctor blade-style process. Wet electrodes are dried in an oven to remove the solvent.

The tuneable control parameters for the coating process are as follows at CPI:

1. Wet coating thickness
2. Drying temperature
3. Drying time

Calendaring the coated electrodes

Coated and dried electrodes are calendared for numerous reasons. These include the improvement of the electronic conductivity between the current collector and the film and increasing the energy density by decreasing the porosity of the films. Calendaring involves pressing the electrode between two rollers at a set distance apart. While reducing the porosity increases the density, some porosity is necessary to allow diffusion of electrolyte into the electrode.

The tuneable control parameters for calendaring are as follows at CPI:

1. Calendaring thickness/density
2. Calendaring speed
3. Calendaring temperature (heating only, no cooling)

Cell assembly

Cells are assembled in either a half or full cell configuration. Half cells incorporate lithium or sodium as a counter electrode for LIB and NIB use case respectively to test the performance of individual anodes or cathodes. Full cells allow the testing of the full battery performance. The electrodes cut to size and stacked with electrolyte and sealed to complete the cells ready for electrical testing. These can be in coin or pouch cell configuration at CPI.

The tuneable control parameters for cell assembly are as follows at CPI:

1. N/P ratio (anode to cathode capacity ratio)
2. N/P area ratio (anode to cathode electrode area ratio)
3. Electrolyte salt (e.g lithium hexafluorophosphate)
4. Electrolyte solvent and solvent mixes (e.g. ethylene carbonate, dimethyl carbonate)
5. Electrolyte volume

Cell testing

Cells are cycled to investigate cell performance. Several cycles at the beginning of the cell cycling lead to the formation of the solid electrolyte interphase (SEI) layer. There is large flexibility in the tunable parameters for the cycling stage, their order and analysis metrics. Comparison of cells cycled under identical protocols is standard.

The tuneable control parameters for cell cycling protocols are as follows at CPI:

1. Resting time
2. Voltage limits (high and low)
3. Current limits for each step
4. Time limits for each step
5. Temperature

6. Cycle C-rate (fast or slow charge/discharge)
7. Cycle number

RFB use case

Redox flow batteries (RFBs) work by storing energy in liquid electrolytes, which flow through the electrochemical cell. Two separate tanks store these electrolytes, which contain dissolved electroactive species. With the use of pumps and pipes, these species circulate between the tanks and the cell. In the cell, electrochemical reactions occur – oxidation (loss of electrons) on the anode and reduction (gain of electrons) on the cathode. The two electrolytes are separated with an ion exchange membrane, which allows maintenance of charge balance.

Figure 2: RFB manufacturing process description

RFBs typically use porous carbon-based electrodes as anodes and cathodes. Carbon felts originating from Polyacrylonitrile (PAN) are commonly used. These electrodes provide a high surface area for electrochemical reactions and enable electrolyte flow through its pores. Advanced design of RFBs includes surface treatments to modify the carbon electrodes to enhance electrode reaction kinetics and electrolyte wettability. Heat or chemical treatments, plasma or electrochemical modifications are commonly used, but the full understanding of why and how these activations work is still missing in the scientific field.

Figure 3: Felt preparation process

The focus of BatCAT project will therefore be on understanding how the surface modification manufacturing step influences the performance of RFBs (Figure 2). In close cooperation of NIC and VANEVO, the number and type of samples, number of process parameter variation steps, process parameter ranges and refinement iterations were discussed and specified. An activation procedure with three steps was designed (Figure 3). In an iterative procedure, the activation of the electrode felt samples are activated and subsequently characterized with various methods by NIC and then sent to VANEVO to be further electrochemically and hydraulically characterized. Based on the results, a new iteration with varied process parameters is planned and performed, aiming at both extending the investigated process parameter domain as well as finding well performing parameter sets and activation procedures.

Characterization methods

Several characterization methods are implemented to assess the samples properties all along the manufacturing processes and also on the final products.

LIB/NIB use case

For LIB and NIB use cases the following characterization methods are in use at CPI in the manufacturing process:

1. Rheology measurement – slurries
2. Photographs – electrode
3. Mass measurements – weight of coated and cut electrodes
4. Resistance measurements – electrode before and after calendaring
5. Thickness measurements – electrode before and after calendaring

Cell cycling – to determine performance

For LIB/NIB use cases, the following characterization will be performed in IFPEN:

Electrode level characterization:

- Novel NMR tests to evaluate microstructure properties
- Symmetric cell measurements:
 - o Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) to assess the tortuosity of manufactured electrodes
- Half-cell manufacturing and testing
 - o Electrode rate capability
 - o GITT tests to measure active material diffusion properties
 - o Aging test in 1C/1D cycles

Full cell characterization

- Coin cell measurements
 - o Slow charge and discharge tests to evaluate electrode balancing
 - o EIS test to assess cell internal impedance
 - o Charge and discharge rate capability tests
 - o HPPC test to assess cell power capability
 - o Aging tests in calendar
- Pouch cell measurements
 - o Slow charge and discharge tests to evaluate electrode balancing
 - o EIS test to assess cell internal impedance
 - o Charge and discharge rate capability tests
 - o HPPC test to assess cell power capability
 - o Aging tests in calendar and cycling aging

For RFB use case, the following characterisation techniques will be used to determine the effect of carbon felt activation:

- Scanning electron microscopy (visualisation of the felt morphology)
- X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (determination of surface specific chemical composition, C1s and O1s spectra will be measured)
- Wetting angle measurement using water and 2 M H₂SO₄ to determine the improvement in wettability
- Raman spectroscopy (information of carbon structure)
- Thickness measurement
- Weight determination

- Electrochemical performance testing including
 - o Energy, voltaic, and coulombic efficiency
 - o Specific capacity and energy
 - o Pressure drop across the felt
 - o Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy

All this characterization techniques will provide the project with various data in terms of type and quantity. This data need to be collected, organised, stored and shared to allow further use along the project.

Data storage and sharing

To ensure a smooth collaboration of partners and WP within the projects, data are made available using the BatCAT SharePoint before the final KB is available to all. This sharing comprises information of the experiments performed on each sample chronologically as well as the manufacturing process of each sample studied in BatCAT.

The global file organization detailed for the LIB use case can be seen in Figure 4.

Figure 4: File storage organization in the BatCAT SharePoint

Characterization master file.

The characterization Masterfile is stored in the T1.1 folder to follow the progress of the experimental campaign.

Sample	LIB-2024-001	LIB-2024-002	LIB-2024-003	LIB-2024-004	LIB-2024-005	LIB-2024-006
Type	Half-cell	Half-cell	Half-cell	Half-cell	Half-cell	Half-cell
Positive sample	NMC_series4_NC.xlsx	NMC_series4_NC.xlsx	NMC_series4_NC.xlsx	NMC_series4_cal1.xlsx	NMC_series4_cal1.xlsx	NMC_series4_cal1.xlsx
Negative sample	Li M					
Cell recipe	Coin cell preparation.xlsx					
Manufacturing time	12/04/2024	12/04/2024	12/04/2024	12/04/2024	12/04/2024	12/04/2024
CPI internal reference	Batcat S4-Uncal	Batcat S4-Uncal	Batcat S4-Uncal	Batcat S4-Cal1	Batcat S4-Cal1	Batcat S4-Cal1
IFPEN internal reference	NMC_series4_NC_prot1	NMC_series4_NC_prot2	NMC_series4_NC_prot3	NMC_series4_cal1_prot1	NMC_series4_cal1_prot2	NMC_series4_cal1_prot3
Overall protocol	Prot 1.xlsx	Prot 2.xlsx	Prot 3.xlsx	Prot 1.xlsx	Prot 2.xlsx	Prot 3.xlsx
Test 1 name	Cell formation					
Test 1 raw data	D051224-01_01_MB_CB1.mpt	D051224-02_01_MB_CB2.mpt	D051224-03_01_MB_CC4.mpt	D051224-04_01_MB_CB3.mpt	D171224-01_01_MB_CA4.mpt	D051224-06_01_MB_CC5.mpt
Test 1 result						
Test 2 name	Check up					
Test 2 raw data	D051224-01_02_MB_CB1.mpt	D051224-02_02_MB_CB2.mpt	D051224-03_02_MB_CC4.mpt	D051224-04_02_MB_CB3.mpt	D171224-01_02_MB_CA4.mpt	D051224-06_02_MB_CC5.mpt
Test 2 result						
Test 3 name	Performance test	GITT test	GITT test	Performance test	GITT test	GITT test
Test 3 raw data	D051224-01_03_MB_CB1.mpt	D051224-02_03_MB_CB2.mpt	D051224-03_03_MB_CC4.mpt	D051224-04_03_MB_CB3.mpt	D171224-01_03_MB_CA4.mpt	D051224-06_03_MB_CC5.mpt
Test 3 result						
Test 4 name	Check up					
Test 4 raw data	D051224-01_04_MB_CB1.mpt	D051224-02_04_MB_CB2.mpt	D051224-03_04_MB_CC4.mpt	D051224-04_04_MB_CB3.mpt	D171224-01_04_MB_CA4.mpt	D051224-06_04_MB_CC5.mpt
Test 4 result						
Test 5 name	Aging	Discharge capability test	Discharge capability test	Aging	Discharge capability test	Discharge capability test
Test 5 raw data	D051224-01_05_MB_CB1.mpt	D051224-02_05_MB_CB2.mpt	D051224-03_05_MB_CC4.mpt	D051224-04_05_MB_CB3.mpt	D171224-01_05_MB_CA4.mpt	D051224-06_05_MB_CC5.mpt
Test 5 result						
Test 6 name	Check up	Charge capability test	Charge capability test	Check up	Charge capability test	Charge capability test
Test 6 raw data	D051224-01_06_MB_CB1.mpt	D051224-02_06_MB_CB2.mpt	D051224-03_06_MB_CC4.mpt	D051224-04_06_MB_CB3.mpt	D171224-01_06_MB_CA4.mpt	D051224-06_06_MB_CC5.mpt
Test 6 result						
Test 7 name		Check up				
Test 7 raw data		D051224-02_07_MB_CB2.mpt	D051224-03_07_MB_CC4.mpt	D171224-01_07_MB_CA4.mpt	D051224-06_07_MB_CC5.mpt	
Test 7 result						
Test 8 name		Aging		Aging		
Test 8 raw data		D051224-02_08_MB_CB2.mpt		D171224-01_08_MB_CA4.mpt		
Test 8 result						
Test 9 name		Check up		Check up		
Test 9 raw data		D051224-02_09_MB_CB2.mpt		D100125-01_09_MB_CA4.mpt		
Test 9 result						

Figure 5: Characterization Masterfile for LIB/NIB usecase

It is an Excel file composed of 3 sheets. The first one is a general explanation of the expected inputs. The second one is dedicated to LIB/NIB use case and the last one is for the RFB use case.

In the first part of the spreadsheet, sample information is given with the sample name, its type (active material, slurry, electrode, half-cell, full cell...). Then the positive sample used is given for half and full cell to link the sample to the manufactured objects described in the recipe files. The manufacturing time is then asked as well as internal IFPEN and CPI references. Finally, the general protocol when available is given. In the next part of the spreadsheet, each test is given through its name from the protocol, a link to the raw data and finally when available a simple result (for instance the available capacity during 1C/1D cycles). An example is shown in Figure 5.

Recipe files

In the recipe files the parameters used to create each sample of BatCAT are described. The goal of these files is to follow the history of each sample throughout the several manufacturing steps used. In this Excel file, each manufacturing step is gathered in a single sheet. In each sheet the column represents a single sample produced during the manufacturing step. It is to be noted that a single sample from a specific step can produce several samples in the following manufacturing steps. For instance, a single slurry in the LIB use case can be used to prepare a dried electrode but this uncalendered dried electrode can be used to create 3 samples of calendered electrodes using different calendaring parameters.

LIB use case

The following steps are described in the LIB use case:

- Mixing
 - o Inputs:
 - Production date
 - Active material
 - Active material D50 μm
 - Additive
 - Slurry solvent
 - Binder
 - Percolant
 - o Parameters
 - Solid content formulation %w
 - Solid content %w
 - Mixing protocol
 - Mixing device
 - o Output
 - Slurry sample
- Coating
 - o Input
 - Slurry sample
 - o Parameters
 - Targeted area capacity mAh/m^2
 - Wet coating gap μm
 - Speed of coating m/s
 - o Output:
 - Coated electrode sample
 - Coated weight achieved g/m^2
- Drying
 - o Input
 - Coated electrode sample
 - Initial density g/m^3
 - o Parameters
 - Initial drying
 - Vacuum drying condition if applicable
 - o Output:
 - Uncalendered (dried) electrode sample
- Calendering
 - o Input

- Uncalendered electrode sample
 - Parameters
 - Calendering density
 - Output:
 - Calendered electrode
 - Final thickness μm
- Cutting
 - Input
 - Electrode sample (uncalendered or calendered)
 - Parameters
 - Cutting shape and size
 - Output
 - Cut electrode subsamples

In Figure 6 is presented an example of the LIB/NIB recipe file dedicated to the mixing step where slurries preparation are presented.

Ouput sample	Unit	Batcat-S3	Batcat-S4	BCA-020-2	LFP400-2	BC-NMC-96-66	BC-NMC-94-66
Production date		18/06/2024	18/06/2024	02/10/2025	01/10/2025	06/04/2025	06/04/2025
Active material		NMC622	NMC622	Graphite	LFP	NMC622	NMC622
Binder		PVDF	PVDF	CMC + SBR	PVDF	PVDF	PVDF
Percolant		Carbon Black	Carbon Black	Carbon Black C45	Carbon Black C65	Carbon Black C65	Carbon Black C65
Solid content formulation	%w	94:03:03	94:03:03	94:02:04	94:03:03	96:02:02	94:03:03
Additive		NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
Slurry solvent		NMP	NMP	Water	NMP	NMP	NMP
Solid content	%w	62	62	44	48	66	66
Mixing protocol		Multi step process					
Mixing device		Robot DAC mixer					
Active material D50	μm	9,9	9,9	17	11	9,9	9,9

Figure 6: Example of LIB/NIB recipe sheet for the mixing step

RFB use case

Data will be stored using the electronic lab notebook eLabFTW on a server and shared with partners. So far the recipe are notherless shared in the SharePoint folder. The 2 main steps considered are the following:

- Thermal oxidation
 - Input:
 - Pristine felt
 - Parameters:
 - Furnace temperature $^{\circ}\text{C}$
 - Heating ramp $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$
 - Time at furnace temperature h
 - Cooling time h
 - Atmosphere
 - Gas flow mL/min
 - Output:
 - Thermally oxidised sample
- Gassification
 - Input:
 - Input felt (usually thermally oxidized felt from step 1)
 - Parameters
 - Furnace temperature $^{\circ}\text{C}$
 - Heating ramp $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$

- Time at furnace temperature h
- Cooling time h
- Atmosphere
- Gas flow mL/min
- Output
 - Functionalized felt

In Figure 7, is presented an extract of the RFB recipe file showing the samples prepared through thermal oxidation.

sample name	units	450_1	450_5	550_1	550_5
input felt		pristine	pristine	pristine	pristine
furnace temperature	°C	450	450	550	550
heating ramp	°C/min	2	2	2	2
time at furnace temperature	h	1	5	1	5
cooling time	h	16	16	16	16
atmosphere		air	air	air	air
gas flow	mL/min	500	500	500	500

Figure 7: Example of RFB recipe file for thermal oxidation

Shared protocols

If needed, specific protocols can be shared among partners to benchmark cell or samples among partners. They are available in the BatCAT SharePoint so that partners can check the specifics of tests performed and if needed rerun them in their own facilities. In the current state LIB coin-cell preparation protocol agreed between CPI and IFPEN are described as well as characterization tests to be performed. In Figure 8, the coin cell preparation and break-in protocol are presented.

Steps	Control type	Set values	Conditions	time
1	Rest	OCV	-	30 s
2	CC Charge	C/10	E _{max}	10 h
3	CV Charge	E _{max} V vs Li ⁺ /Li	I limit	10 mns
4	Rest	OCV	-	2s
5	CC Discharge	C/10	E _{min}	10h
6	CV Discharge	E _{min}	I limit	10 mns
7	Rest	OCV	-	2s
8	CC Charge	C/10	E _{max}	10 h
9	CV Charge	E _{max} V vs Li ⁺ /Li	I limit	10 mns
10	Rest	OCV	-	1h
11	CC Discharge	C/10	E _{min}	10h
12	CV Discharge	E _{min}	I limit	10 mns
13	Rest	OCV	-	1h
14	CC Charge	C/10	E _{intermediate}	10 h
15	CV Charge	E _{intermediate}	I limit	10 mns
16	PEIS	10 kHz to 10 mHz E=10 mV	-	30 mns
17	CC Charge	C/10	E _{max}	10 h
18	CV Charge	E _{max}	I limit	10 mns
19	Rest	OCV	-	1h
20	CC Discharge	C/20	E _{min}	20h
21	Rest	OCV	-	1h

Figure 8: LIB coin cell preparation protocol

Experimental campaign plan

He will be described the initial experimental campaign plan and the next steps planned for the BatCAT project

LIB/NIB use case

- 1) Calendering impact assessment

The objective of this first step is to assess the workflow between CPI and IFPEN and finalize characterization protocols at the electrode level.

- a. Manufacturing of 3 calendered electrodes and 1 uncalendered electrode using NMC622 active material
 - b. Electrode characterization
- 2) Active material impact

Following the initial work on NMC the second batch of electrodes is produced using LFP and Graphite electrodes

- a. Manufacturing of LFP and Graphite electrodes
 - 3 calendered and 1 uncalendered graphite electrode
 - 1 uncalendered and 1 uncalendered LFP electrode
 - b. Electrode characterization
- 3) Formulation impact

Using the initial NMC622 batch as a reference, a new slurry is produced with its subsequent electrode to investigate the impact of binder and percolant content on cell performance.

- a. Manufacturing of NMC622 electrodes with 96:2:2 formulation
 - b. Electrode characterization
- 4) Full cell characterization

Using several electrode manufacturing parameters, full cell characterization will be performed to assess cell performance in terms of power and energy as well as lifetime

- 5) Sodium ion test campaign

A faster experimental campaign will be performed using sodium-ion materials comprising the effect of calendaring and formulation.

RFB use case

- 1) Felt thermal oxidation
 - a. Thermal oxidation: evaluation of thermal parameters impact (furnace temperature, and time)
 - b. Felt characterization
- 2) Felt gasification
 - a. Impact of atmosphere (gas flow and thermal operating conditions)
 - b. Felt characterization
- 3) Cell performance evaluation

Full cell characterization will be performed to evaluate the impact of felt preparation on electrochemical behaviour in full cells.

3. Conclusion

This deliverable provides the initial effort of WP1 in order to structure the experimental work to be performed in the BatCAT project. It provides an exhaustive list of manufacturing steps studied within the project as well

as their respective tuneable parameters and outputs. Then it provides the possible characterization methods available to characterize the samples generated throughout the project.

Finally, data storage system and taxonomy are described. The objective is to make experimental data available as soon as possible in agreement with WP4 developments. As we study the manufacturing of cells, it is mandatory to be able to trace back the origin of each component of the final cell and the manufacturing parameters used. This is ensured thanks to the “recipe” files present in the BatCAT SharePoint. Further information such as shared protocol can also be found in the SharePoint.

This data storage system is nevertheless a provisional solution adopted while the final knowledge base is completely available. It will be used in return to correctly set the knowledge base as every information available today in these files must be present in the final storage system.

Finally, by providing this deliverable, it will be possible to adjust the next steps of the experimental campaign to fit the requirements of other beneficiaries of BatCAT. Especially, the choice of active materials for the NIB will be done in agreement between CPI and WP2 members knowledge of available active materials.